

AU-EU Cooperation on Returns: Understanding Transregional Dialogues and Contesting Regional Mobility Agendas

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List of abbreviations

AfCFTA	The African Continental Free Trade Area
AU	African Union
AUC	African Union Commission
AUC DSA	AU Department of Social Affairs
AVRR	Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration
C2CMMD	AU-EU Continent-to-Continent Migration and Mobility Dialogue
CSO	Civil Society Organizations
ECOWAS	Economic Community of West African States
EU	European Union
GAPs	Decentering the Study of Migrant Returns and Readmission Policies in Europe and Beyond
GIZ	Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit
ICMPD	International Center for Migration Policy Development
IOM	International Organization for Migration
JVAP	Joint Valletta Action Plan
MMD	Migration and Mobility Dialogue Support Program
MME	The Joint Africa- Europe Strategic Partnership on Migration, Mobility, and Employment
MPFA	African Union Migration Policy Framework for Africa and Plan of Action
PFMP	African Union Protocol on the Freedom of Movement People
REC	Regional Economic Community
RRR	Return, Readmission, and Reintegration
STC	Specialized Technical Committee

Abstract

Several studies on return diplomacy focus on how the EU and its member states use their power and resources to shape negotiation outcomes and control migration by developing bilateral, regional, and inter-regional mechanisms and through international organizations. As a result, studies on return (migration) diplomacy either look at negotiations from a top-down standpoint, highlighting the inherent Eurocentrism of migration diplomacy, or the bilateral negotiations between the EU, member states, and third countries and how non-EU countries navigate the power of asymmetries in their negotiations, as well as the EU's turn to informality in negotiating returns. As a result, there is a general research gap on return diplomacy between African regional and supranational bodies and a specific research gap on developing a continent-wide and intra-regional approach in Africa to the EU's return diplomacy. This study aims to address this gap and focuses on understanding the place return occupies in the AU's existing migration policy frameworks and studying the AU's approach to return and readmission. With a mix of tools including a review of relevant policy papers and expert interviews, this study seeks to understand transregional dialogues and contesting regional mobility agendas and contribute to efforts to understand the interests and perspectives of actors in the Global South.

Keywords: return, return diplomacy, African Union, return cooperation

1. Introduction¹

Return diplomacy is a process through which states use diplomatic processes, tools, and partnerships for their return goals and objectives.² Studies have shown how the EU uses its power and resources to shape negotiation outcomes and control migration by developing bilateral, regional, and inter-regional mechanisms and through international organizations. Betts (2011) centers the EU as the main actor in migration governance norm diffusion and mediation and negotiation and designates African actors such as the African Union (AU) and regional economic communities such as the Intergovernmental Authority on Development IGAD as the institutions through which the EU diffuses its norms including those relating to migration and border control and return and readmission. This perspective overlooks intra-regional dialogue and norms and how that may also significantly impact regional and continent-wide approaches to migration governance and return.

Several studies share this same perspective, and instead of focusing on the EU at the top of the migration governance totem pole, analyze how EU funding for development and security is exchanged for implementing border and migration control initiatives in specific African countries (Trauner & Deimel 2013; Bisong 2020; and Mouthaan 2021). Empirical research also shows that non-EU countries actively engage with and make sense of migration governance in their negotiations to fit their domestic interests (Van Criekinge 2009; Paoletti 2011; Cassarino 2011; Strange and Martin 2019, and Adam et al 2020). For example, Adam et al. (2020) study the policy goals of West African actors and highlight the factors that shape West African migration policy preferences and negotiations, using Ghana and Senegal as case studies to show how West African actors navigate and utilize migration governance for their interests. Instead of studying powerful states and institutions and their processes or how they impact less powerful counterparts, Lavenex and Piper (2021) focus on the multi-dimensional nature of migration governance and the interactions between governments (from above), civil society (from below), and external actors (from beyond) involved in regional dialogues and consultations. According to this perspective, regional migration governance is significant and should be treated as its process rather than a process created, and influenced by international institutions and powerful states only.

Studies focused specifically on return (migration) diplomacy either look at negotiations from a top-down standpoint, highlighting the inherent Eurocentrism of migration diplomacy (Tolay 2022, Roig and Huddleston 2007, Lisiecka & Parkes 2017) or the bilateral negotiations between the EU and third countries and how non-EU countries navigate the power of asymmetries in their negotiations (Janvier 2023, Fernández-Molina & De Larramendi 2022, Kaiser 2019, Adamson & Tsourapas 2018, İçduygu & Aksel 2014, and Wolff 2014), as well as the EU's turn to informality in negotiating returns (Cassarino 2009, Cassarino and Giuffrè 2017; Slagter 2019; Sahin-Mencütek & Triandafyllidou 2024). Others unpack the politics of return because implementing

¹ The author would like to thank the Canada Excellence Research Chair in Migration and Integration Anna Triandafyllidou (Toronto Metropolitan University), GAPs co-coordinator Zeynep Mencütek (Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies), and GAPs partner, Gerasimos Tsourapas (University of Glasgow) for their constructive comments and suggestions which greatly improved the report. Finally, the author would like to thank all the research participants who shared their time, insight, and expertise to enrich the report.

² Return in this report refers to coerced return, rather than the broader concept of migrant return. This definition follows the discussion on the relationship between return and coercion discussed in the GAPs Concept paper as part of the effort to decenter the study of returns by including migrant perspectives on return and the ambiguousness of voluntariness in migrant journeys (Sahin-Mencütek, Z. Triandafyllidou, A., Barthoma, S., Nimmer, M., Rottmann, S., Öztürk, N. and R. Istaiteyeh (2023). "Framework paper on the concepts and typologies on returns, combined with four conceptual notes" in *Global Migration: Consequences and Responses* Vol.1: 78, Uppsala: Acta Universitatis Upsaliensis, p- 7-11).

return initiatives is tied to the politics and geopolitical interests of sending and receiving states (for example, Mencuttek 2022). Geddes & Maru (2020) localize migration diplomacy in Africa by studying Ethiopia's migration diplomacy within the region and concerning supranational bodies such as the AU and the EU and compare and contrast regional and international approaches to return and reintegration. Tsourapas (2017) similarly localizes Libya's migration diplomacy with regional and international actors and how mobility shapes issue linkages in negotiations. These studies raise questions about the diplomacy of African regional or supranational bodies specifically, whether there is an African approach to return diplomacy, what this approach is, and how African actors navigate the norms and interests of powerful external actors such as the EU and the challenges of negotiating despite asymmetries of power. Return diplomacy through this perspective is missing and this is mainly because the focus has been on either the unilateral goals and measures of the EU, its bilateral cooperation with specific states, or the bilateral cooperation between EU member states and single African countries.

There is a general research gap on return diplomacy between regional and supranational bodies and a specific research gap on the continent-wide and intra-regional approach in Africa to the EU's return diplomacy. This study aims to address this gap and focuses on understanding the place return occupies in the AU's existing migration policy frameworks and studying the AU's approach to return and readmission. With a mix of tools including a review of relevant policy papers and expert interviews, this study seeks to understand transregional dialogues and contesting regional mobility agendas and contribute to efforts to better understand the interests and perspectives of actors in the Global South and makes empirical, methodological, and analytical contributions to this field.

The working paper is organized into four parts: the first part is the introduction, which delineates the research objectives, questions, significance, and methodology. Part 2 has two parts that focus on understanding the AU's participation in EU-led processes on the one hand, and AU-led processes on the other hand. Part 3 focuses on the findings of the expert interviews and will be broken into three parts: the AU's pan-African approach to return, the limitations to AU return diplomacy, and the role of third parties in AU-EU return dialogue. The last part of the paper will be the conclusion of the study, which is a short reflection on the future of AU-EU cooperation on returns based on the research findings.

1.1 Brief Background of AU-EU Migration Cooperation

The transcontinental cooperation between Africa and the EU began at the EU-Africa Summit in Cairo in 2000, but migration was not the focus until the 2007 Africa-EU summit in Lisbon. Through Joint Africa- Europe Strategic Partnership on Migration, Mobility, and Employment (MME), the AU and EU aligned for transregional migration dialogue with a focus on human trafficking, irregular migration, remittances, diaspora, and labour migration. Within the theme of irregular migration, the EU's return and readmission goals were central; as a result, as early as 2007, return diplomacy between the AU and the EU was in practice. The EU has advanced migration management in Africa through the African Union through the creation of migration dialogue platforms such as the EU-AU dialogue on migration, the Joint Africa- EU Declaration on Migration and Development, the MME, as well as extensive funding in a wide range of sectors including trade, development, security, and migration. The AU has also used this funding for capacity building of Regional Economic Communities (RECs) to cooperate on migration and to disseminate an EU-type combination of REC-style freedom of movement with migration management (Betts 2011).

Betts argues that persuasion, (altering another's beliefs), bargaining (coercing another actor using a carrot and stick approach), and emulation, (setting out the standards to be practiced) are tools that have influenced the AU and EU transregional dialogue. According to this argument, the IOM

engages in persuasion, and AU- EU engagement has been through a mix of bargaining and emulation with the AU using diplomacy to set the desirable standards of practice in the continent relating to regional integration and most recently, return and readmission and this will be discussed in more detail in this paper.

The 2015 Valletta Summit set a more aggressive tone for the EU's return diplomacy as a mix of diplomacy, financial incentives; and partnerships on aid, security, and development, and were deployed to serve the return and readmission agenda, which became the leading issue in both bilateral and multilateral negotiations between the EU/ member states and the AU/ member states (Dennison et al. 2019).³ After the Valletta Summit, there was a renaissance of the integration and free movement agenda through the AU and its RECs. Free movement regimes are particularly relevant to the EU in easing migration pressure to Europe, as Africans move about more on the continent (Parks and McQuay 2020). This is the reason for both EU and AU engagement with Freedom of movement regimes in the RECs and the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA).

Since the Valetta Summit, the EU partnership has been criticized for focusing on return and readmission and undermining the AU's pan-African agenda and continent-to-continent dialogue. Post-Valetta, the EU has favored bilateral partnerships with individual countries and RECs (Mehari 2023). The return agenda has also interfered with the freedom of movement regimes in RECs such as ECOWAS and by extension, the freedom of movement initiatives of the AU (Bisong 2020).

To give context on the increasing practice of returns, the International Organization (IOM)'s Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration (AVRR) program increased by 24 per cent in 2022 (from 43,428 in 2021 to 54,001 in 2022), and about half of those returned were returned to African countries (IOM, 2023).⁴ Funding for returns has also been on the rise.⁵ The availability of funding for different aspects and challenges of return and readmission enables increased engagement of states in return, readmission, and reintegration (RRR) initiatives led by the EU in individual African states through bilateral agreements. With this context and the increasing number of migrant returns and EU and EU member state funding for returns in recent years, there has been an increasing need to better understand and center the AU's position on return and readmission standards in Africa.

This context and the need to center, delineate, and understand the AU's position is what informs the focus of this paper. As a result, it aims to do the following:

³ The European Union (EU) has a significant influence on migration in Africa through the European Union Emergency Trust Fund for Africa (EUTF). The EUTF, signed by 25 EU member states, Norway, and Switzerland, was launched in November 2015 at the Valletta Summit on Migration, with a total commitment of €5 billion. This fund supports 204 initiatives in 26 African countries. Additionally, the EU has allocated funds for African migration management, including €30.5 billion from the European Development Fund, €3.6 billion from the Internal Security Fund for borders and visas, €676 million from the Return Fund, and €1.8 billion from the External Borders Fund, along with more than 63 agreements and memoranda of understanding, including the Migration Partnership Framework.

⁴ These numbers from the IOM refer to returned migrants.

⁵ For example, in 2016, the European Union (EU) funded the EU Readmission Capacity Building Facility (EURCAP) with 38.5 million Euros to build the capacity of selected countries of origin to manage return and cooperate on readmission with the EU. See IOM <<https://eea.iom.int/european-readmission-capacity-building-facility> eurcap#:~:text=The%20EURCAP%20Facility%20aims%20at,Affairs%20with%2038.5%20million%20eu ro.>

- a) Understand the AU's approach to return diplomacy and understand how the AU pushes its perspective and shapes continental approaches and the transcontinental and intercontinental dialogue
- b) Gain insight into the future of the AU's return diplomacy based on current realities and insights from experts.

This paper aims to contribute to the larger aim of the GAPs project to decenter the study of return and readmissions by making the perspectives and approaches to return in the Global South the focal point. In this case, the focus is on the AU, its priorities and goals, and the potential and limitations of its approach to return. Finally, this is significant because of the dissemination of these perspectives and approaches in research and knowledge production about migration and migration diplomacy.

1.2 Research Methodology

To understand the place return holds within the AU's existing migration policy framework, as well as the AU's approach to return, this study employs a mix of tools including the review of relevant policy papers about the AU's migration policy, AU internal documents and workshop notes about approaches to return and readmission, as well as interviews with experts both within and outside the institution who have participated in stakeholder dialogue platforms.

The interview phase of the research spanned three months (April to July 2024) and took place virtually due to the diverse schedules and locations of the participants. A total of 8 experts from the African Union Commission (AUC), the EU, an African migration policy center, an AU member state migration parastatal, an African university, and migration policy consulting firms were interviewed about the African Union's perspective and return diplomacy. Experts are defined as actors actively engaged in return and readmission dialogues and research relating to the African Union and its member states.

All interviewees' names have been anonymized or changed to protect their privacy. Interviewees were informed of the research's purpose and dissemination. Interviews were transcribed and annotated, and the data was conceptualized and analyzed.

2. Contextualizing the AU's Engagement on Return and Readmission in the Past Decade

2.1 Participation in EU-led dialogue after the 2015 Joint Valletta Action Plan

There have been several forums for dialogue on migration through which the AU has been engaged on the issue of return and readmission with the EU and other actors since the Joint Valletta Action Plan (JVAP) in 2015. For example, the Support Project to the Africa-EU Migration and Mobility Dialogue (MMD) has aimed to promote organized, secure, and ethical migration and mobility of individuals within Africa and between Africa and Europe since 2017. This initiative is a component of the Joint Africa-EU Strategy and currently in its third phase, the project seeks to endorse migration dialogues facilitated by the International Centre for Migration Policy Development (ICMPD) (the Rabat Process, Khartoum Process, and the AU-EU Continent-to-Continent Migration and Mobility Dialogue) and to monitor the progress of the JVAP. Furthermore, the project also backs various initiatives from local authorities, civil society organizations (CSOs), and diaspora organizations through competitive grants.

Through this dialogue, representatives from the AU, EU, and RECs have participated in multiple discussion events on migration and mobility alongside national and international experts, academics, and businesses. These dialogues have aimed to create a deeper understanding of the perspectives of each party, the sharing of knowledge, resources, and expertise among stakeholders, and improvements in mobility and migration frameworks. The activities were noted to have encouraged the exchange of information and best practices. Importantly initiating and continuing of the dialogue despite political challenges are accomplishments in themselves (Mehari 2023). Mehari argues that the MMD advances key areas of cooperation and helps to foster trust between the two parties. It also facilitated the identification of common ground, the narrowing of differences, and the expansion of political support for ongoing collaboration. Projects developed following high-level political consensus were relatively easier to execute, such as the African Institute of Remittances (AIR) and Free Movement protocols.

The AU-EU Continent-to-Continent Migration and Mobility Dialogue (C2CMMD), rooted in the 2017 AU-EU Summit in Abidjan and the 2019 meeting of AU-EU Ministers in Brussels and implemented as part of the wider EU-funded MMD, was created to expand dialogue on migration and mobility between Africa and Europe. These two meetings also aimed to deepen cooperation on the AU Migration Policy Framework for Africa and Plan of Action (MPF), the AU Protocol on the Freedom of Movement of People (PFMP), and the Joint Valetta Action Plan. The C2CMMD has three main objectives including a framework for transregional consultation and coordination, dealing with migration challenges at the continental and inter-regional levels, and providing partnership opportunities and shared responsibility. The C2CMMD operates on the principle of subsidiarity and follows national, regional, and global ambitions and policies on migration and mobility. Return and readmission is one of the thematic focus areas of the C2CMMD, creating a platform through which the AU and EU can engage in return diplomacy.

A study examining return, readmission, and reintegration programs in Africa was commissioned by the ICMPD on behalf of the AU and the EU. The African Union Commission (AUC) was the primary beneficiary of this study, and the EU provided funding for this project through the MMD. This study aimed to understand the cohesive principles and approaches that apply to the AU member states for sustainable RRR and examined programs in five sub-regions of the continent and 9 AU member states. This study is important because it attempts to delineate the African approach to return in practice and take the experiences of returned migrants across the continent into consideration (see ICMPD 2021). The study tries to determine which stakeholders should be included in RRR strategies and interventions following the existing continental frameworks. The report noted that African regions that have experienced a particular outflow and return of persons have attempted to develop specific RRR legal and policy frameworks (e.g. West African states have legal provisions on irregular migration, and the Horn of Africa region has also developed policy or draft instruments focused on RRR through the Intergovernmental Authority on Development (IGAD)) However, as this study showed how approaches in Africa are disconnected between framework and implementation at regional and national levels.

As part of the initiatives of the C2CMMD, the AUC and the ICMPD have also focused on disseminating messaging shaped by this transcontinental dialogue to national-level policymakers, regional governments, media practitioners, civil society organizations, as well as academics.⁶ This

⁶ See African Union Quarterly Newsletter on Migration and Mobility (Jan – June 2023). Accessible at < <https://au.int/sites/default/files/documents/43174-doc-AU-LEM-NEWSLETTER-ENG-.pdf>>, p. 12. The AUC and the ICMPD organized a "Training of Trainers" (ToT) in Kenya, certifying participants from across the African continent to train for the AU Migration Governance Training Program. The AUC plans to utilize these trainers to provide training for AU member states. Additionally, two other 3-day training courses titled "Making Migration Work for Africa" and "Migration in Africa – Myths and Reality" were in development. These initiatives are part of the EU-funded MMD to the African Union.

dissemination of standards and the ideal of migration governance is akin to Betts's argument of the role of persuasion, bargaining, and emulation in shaping the continental and regional approaches to migration governance and by extension, return and readmission.

Part of the C2CMMD, the AU–EU–UN Tripartite Taskforce on the Situation of Migrants and Refugees is another mechanism through which the AU is engaged in return diplomacy led by the EU alongside the UN, IOM, and AU member states. Set up after the 5th AU-EU Summit in 2017, the task force aims to save the lives of migrants in Libya, and the AU, EU, and UN have met several times since then at technical and political levels on the issue of the return of migrants on the route to or in Libya to their countries of origin. This enabled the initiation of a large-scale program for assisting and supporting the voluntary return of migrants, as well as the evacuation operation. This initiative has resulted in more than 48,000 voluntary migrant returns with the assistance of IOM and AU Member States, and over 4,000 refugees being evacuated from Libya by UNHCR.⁷ The most recent meeting in 2023 highlighted the need for the expansion of non-discriminatory legal and policy frameworks rooted in both international and AU standards for the return of migrants in Libya.⁸ This shows the growing significance of the AU standards in the norms and practices of return of not only external actors such as the EU and its member states but also AU member states where migrants transit or are returned to.

An AUC official commented on the AU's engagement in these EU-led dialogues and processes, noting that these existing frameworks have not been used to their full potential despite these developments due to political reasons:

While there has been continent-to-continent dialogue on mobility to address elements from the plan of action, joint declarations, coordination in the secretariat, ministerial and commissioners meetings between the AU and EU to agree on points, and high-level meetings between AU and EU member states with the most recent one in Kigali, migration has remained a thorny issue because there has not been follow up to Valetta the way it was agreed in the plan of action. The existing frameworks are not used to their full potential for political reasons: EU interests may not be achieved through a transcontinental framework, so it approaches African member states individually, as a result, the AU as a bloc is challenged.⁹

Specifically on the Joint Plan of Action (JVAP) and its follow-up, the official opined that it was expected that the plan would address the concerns of both actors, in a balanced conversation, and the constant back and forth has made return and readmission dialogue difficult. Also, there are expectations from the sending countries regarding support in returning the migrants but also addressing the conditions that made them leave in the first place. Additionally, the EU pact on migration and asylum did not consult with Africans, but the outcomes of that pact are to be

⁷ International Organization of Migration (IOM) (2019). Joint Press Release: Meeting of the Joint AU-EU-UN Taskforce to Address the Migrant and Refugee Situation in Libya. Accessible at < <https://www.iom.int/news/joint-press-release-meeting-joint-au-eu-un-taskforce-address-migrant-and-refugee-situation-libya> >

⁸ See European Commission (2017). Joint press release of the United Nations, the African Union, and the European Union. Accessible at https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/STATEMENT_17_5029, See also, IOM (2019). Joint Press Release: Meeting of the Joint AU-EU-UN Taskforce to Address the Migrant and Refugee Situation in Libya. Accessible at < <https://www.iom.int/news/joint-press-release-meeting-joint-au-eu-un-taskforce-address-migrant-and-refugee-situation-libya> >, and UNHCR (2023), Joint Press Release: AU, EU and UN push for urgent action to address the pressing needs of migrants and refugees in Libya. Accessible at: < <https://www.unhcr.org/news/press-releases/au-eu-and-un-push-urgent-action-address-pressing-needs-migrants-and-refugees> >.

⁹ Zoom Interview with AUC official, May 15, 2024 (on file with author).

implemented with collaboration from AU member states. The result is what the AUC official called a “double game” where conversations are happening, but the real actions of the EU and its member states such as the agreement with Niger impede both regional (West African) and continental rights such as freedom of movement. The real expectations of both the AU/ its member states and the EU/ its member states remain at odds and unfulfilled as a result.

Mehari (2023) highlights this mismatch, explaining that state control over ports and immigration is an act of sovereignty and that the presence of European immigration officials in Africa challenges African sovereignty. For example, France has staff stationed in countries such as Cameroon to handle returns, whereas Cameroon does not have a RRR policy framework. Additionally, Mehari uses the example of private agencies hired by destination countries and stationed in Northern African countries and major airports to question the accountability of the EU in cases of human rights violations. The EU has focused on returning and readmitting individuals, an aspect of sovereignty involving nationality and entry requirements. Mehari adds that the EU's "carrot and stick" approach to improving return and readmission rates by African states has shown little effectiveness and may have long-term negative consequences and the idea of legal pathways as a deterrent to irregular migration is Eurocentric and contradicts real-life experiences, such as data showing repeated return migration of individuals deported to Africa from regions like the Middle East, where migrants face degrading treatment.

Focusing on the concerns of only one party jeopardizes the sustainability of return diplomacy. As a result, the return dialogue is not moving in the direction both parties want despite all efforts; cooperation on return has gone backward despite the increasing number of forums for dialogue over time because of the double game in EU-led dialogue since 2015.

2.2 The AU's frameworks for return and the development of continental standards for return and readmission

Nevertheless, the AU has been gradually building frameworks to address return and readmission challenges. Based on the context of the challenges of the migration of Africans and its implication for the future of the continent, the OAU Council of Ministers decided to develop a Migration Policy Framework (MPF) in 2006 on a continental strategic framework for migration policy to address migration challenges, focused on freedom of movement and cooperation and the participation of migrants in the diaspora. The MPF was implemented, providing comprehensive and integrated policy recommendations for AU Member States and RECs. These entities were urged to consider these guidelines as they worked to promote migration and development and tackle migration issues in Africa. The guidelines covered nine main areas: Labor Migration, Border Management, Irregular Migration, Forced Displacement, Human Rights of Migrants, Internal Migration, Migration Data Management, Migration and Development, and Inter-State cooperation and partnerships.

The AU recently implemented policies to improve migration management within Africa and between Africa and other regions of the world. These policies emphasize the need to address return migration and reintegration in respectful and sustainable ways, as outlined in the 2015 Common African Union Position on Humanitarian Effectiveness and the 2016 New York Declaration for Refugees and Migrants. In 2016, the AUC assessed the effectiveness of the MPF in guiding Member States and RECs in managing migration, identified challenges in its implementation, explored potential opportunities, assessed its ongoing relevance, and considered the need for revision. Upon completing the evaluation, AU Member States and RECs convened in 2016 to examine the assessment report of the African Union Migration Policy Framework for Africa. They recognized the evolving nature of migration and the changing migration patterns in Africa over the past decade. As a result, they recommended that the AUC update the MPF and develop a 10-year plan for its implementation. Consequently, the revised MPF (referred to as

MPFA from hereon) encompasses the current migration dynamics in Africa and presents an updated strategic framework to direct Member States and RECs in managing migration. The 2006 MPF has been updated to address present migration trends and effectively advise AU Member States and RECs on migration management. The MPFA outlines eight main pillars with sub-themes and offers policy suggestions for AU Member States and RECs to consider. It presents detailed policy recommendations on specific thematic issues and their respective sub-themes.

The MPFA acts as a strategy and roadmap for AU member states and RECs to achieve the overall aim of efficient migration governance. The initial MPF did not include return specifically, however, the MPFA identifies eight key pillars, of which the fifth is irregular migration- return, readmission, and integration fall under this pillar as subthemes. Advancements have been achieved in the return, readmission, and reintegration (RRR) programs on the African continent with the guidance of the AU, offering valuable insights and best practices.

The MPFA delineates what return, readmission, and reintegration mean and highlights the importance of the role of cooperation and mutual understanding between states (in other words diplomacy), in the context of North-South relations for effective, safe, humane policies and mechanisms for return and readmission.¹⁰ The key part of this subtheme in the MPFA is the recommended strategies for the future, this is because these strategies show not only the challenges of return according to the AU, but also the actions to be taken in the future. The recommended strategies include creating standards and procedures, based on law and policy, for the return, re-admission, and reintegration of migrants in line with relevant international legal instruments, ensuring that return and readmission agreements do not compromise freedom of movement on the continent, the prevention of irregular migration by member states through the establishment of inter-state and intra-regional procedures, support for transit countries, measures to encourage voluntary departure and return, and enhanced regional cooperation on return and readmission in an orderly, human and gender-responsive manner. The evaluation of RRR programs on the continent and setting of best practices and standards based on international law was planned to be executed by the AUC Department of Social Affairs (AUC DSA) within 4-5 years after the revision of the MPFA with the goal of the creation of continental RRR guidelines for member states to follow.¹¹

The MPFA takes a progressive approach to return by supporting measures to prevent further irregular migration and recommends gender- and human rights-responsive returns and readmissions. It advocates for sustainable reintegration aligned with national development strategies, considering the unique circumstances of returnees and their communities. The AUC has identified key steps and measures for the sustainable reintegration of returning migrants into the labor market. Additionally, the Commission held a workshop to initiate discussions on the sustainable reintegration of migrants into their origin communities. Conclusions highlighted the need for the development of continental return, re-admission, and reintegration guidelines for effective use by AU Member States.

From the wording of the MPFA, the AU's attitude to return is clear; some of the key aspects include inter-state dialogue, cooperation and mutual understanding on contentious issues, the prevention of irregular migration, and the significance of upholding gender and human rights responsive returns and readmissions in an orderly, safe and dignified manner, as well as the development of sustainable reintegration that matches existing national development strategies and interests, taking the unique needs and circumstances of returnees and their communities.

¹⁰ See MFPA p. 54

¹¹ See MFPA Plan of Action (Return and Readmission subtheme)

The AUC outlined steps for the sustainable reintegration of returning migrants into the labor market, following a workshop in October 2018. Additionally, a joint workshop with AU and EU Member States in November 2018 emphasized the need for the continental return, readmission, and reintegration guidelines to be used by AU Member States, considering individual and community needs, and implementing structural interventions through a whole-of-government approach.

As a result, it was in fulfillment of this action plan that the EU-funded research project on RRR on the continent was commissioned by the ICMPD for the AU (mentioned earlier). An expert spoke on the process leading to the drafting of the continental guidelines, highlighting the core aims of the guidelines, the main problem with return diplomacy according to the AU perspective, and the simultaneous development of an intracontinental return diplomacy process:

We did have several meetings mostly in Kenya. In 2020/2021, there was a conversation about how to harmonize responses when it comes to return, readmission, and reintegration issues on the continent. A consultant was hired at the time to do a background study to look at the main issues and the gaps and potential ways of dealing with this. Then the decision was made to come up with a set of continental guidelines on return, re-admission, and integration. They came out with draft guidelines for member states to look through and potentially adapt as a continental document that will guide how they deal with written issues. One of the concerns was that different member states were doing different things with different partners, and they wanted to standardize their approach. So, when it comes to return, for instance, there will be a standard AU approach to dealing with return agreements, dealing with issues of people being deported, and so on. And beyond that to sustainably have people who have returned, whether voluntarily or involuntarily to be sustainably reintegrated into their communities. You see, the initial draft of the guidelines that I attended a couple of sessions where we made input as experts, then they also developed they involved a civil Society, and organizations as well. So initially it was member states but then when it came to the validation processes and getting broader input from different sectors, they involved the CSOs and then independent experts in Mombasa and we went through the draft document to fine-tune it to bring on board the issues that are important to the private sector, to civil society and development partners who are part of that as well.¹²

The purpose of the draft continental Guidelines for the RRR of migrants is to create common standards, principles, and collective action through AU to help member states standardize their policies, regulations, and laws on Return, Re-admission, and improve conditions for sustainable re-integration. The draft guidelines foster common responsibilities of countries of origin and destination; responsibilities specific to countries of origin; responsibilities specific to countries of transit; responsibilities specific to countries of destination; bilateral and regional cooperation; and recommendations concerning monitoring and reporting.

The AUC led the drafting process, which involved discussions in 2022 with experts from AU member states, RECs, independent experts, CSOs, and international organizations. The consultations emphasized the need for practical tools, including standard operating procedures for return and reintegration, a model agreement, and terms of reference for national coordination mechanisms. These tools and the revised guidelines require review by experts from Member States and RECs before final approval from AU organs. In 2023, a technical workshop was held as part of the consultation process. Experts from AU Member States, RECs, civil society

¹² Zoom Interview with Return and Readmission Expert/ Consultant, July 17, 2024 (on file with author).

organizations, and international organizations gathered to review the draft continental guidelines on RRR and the operationalization tools. The workshop aimed to share practical experience on the return and reintegration processes of African migrants, draw lessons from existing tools for return and reintegration, and revise the draft guidelines for validation and approval by relevant AU organs.

This reveals a detailed ongoing development of extensive intra-continental processes to shape the AU and its member states engagement with different external actors in return and readmission diplomacy to counter the intercontinental/ transregional dialogues and contesting regional mobility agendas among AU member states in their engagement with the EU as a bloc and with EU member states. An expert indicated that these continental standards are created to apply beyond actors in Europe as well:

...it's a necessary action that the AU is taking, and it's not necessarily just limited to their relations with the EU only because, you know, we have even bigger challenges with the Gulf States because lots of domestic workers are going there. There are issues of abuse. There are issues of mass deportations- over 100,000 people were brought back to Ethiopia from Saudi Arabia alone. You know, and no questions asked because they don't claim respect for human rights, this is really unlike the EU. The EU is quite careful in the way they are perceived. They are worried about reputational harm and the rest of it. The Gulf states send people back, no questions are asked about whether they are victims of abuse and whatnot. They don't react in the same way. So, the expectation is that these guidelines could be used in other contexts beyond AU-EU relations. So, if you have return in the context of Arab or Gulf States, these things could be looked at...¹³

As a result, beyond the AU-EU return dialogue, having continental return standards can also create frameworks for dialogue and migrant protection in other contexts and with other external actors where there is or has been very little dialogue. This is the significance of the AU's focus on continental return and readmission standards-setting in its return diplomacy with the rest of the world.

3. The Potential and Limitations of AU Return Diplomacy

This section below unpacks the dynamics of AU return diplomacy from expert insights, rather than the analysis of formal documents because the normalization of a continental approach to return is unfolding; we can learn what this normalization process is from stakeholders engaged in this ongoing process. Additionally, while formal documents provide the contents of policy, they do not reveal the nuances and the power dynamics of implementation. Governance and diplomacy are influenced not only by formal agreements and documents but especially by power dynamics and the interests of powerful actors in protecting their interests (Tsourapas 2021). These interests may be disguised in intercontinental agreements and supranational return dialogue but reveal themselves in other ways including norm/ standard creation, priority/ agenda setting and implementation, funding, and the unequal relations of the EU with different AU member states, etc.

¹³ Zoom Interview with Return and Readmission Expert/ Consultant, July 17, 2024 (on file with author).

3.1 Continental Standards as a Pan-African approach to return diplomacy

Standards-setting among its member states and RECs has been the AU's key approach to migration diplomacy with the EU on several issues. For example, the AU has used its cooperation with the EU to develop and expand regional standards and institutional measures to address human trafficking. The AU Commission Initiative Against Trafficking (AU.COMMIT), was set up by the AU to work with the EU, member states, RECs, civil society organizations, development partners, the media, and academic institutions on the issue of human trafficking, to develop and implement regional action plans and institutional measures and the operationalization of the Ouagadougou Plan of Action against Trafficking in Human Beings (Mehari 2023). This is the same approach the AU is taking towards the issue of return.

However, despite the existing frameworks and dialogue, and the ongoing process to develop continental guidelines discussed above, the AU still does not have an official position on return. An AUC official stated that though the institution has no official position, return is outlined in the MPFA and migration is part of African history, culture, and development the AU acknowledges the challenges of managing contemporary migration and recognizes that return migration has a lot of potential and some positive aspects which have not been given proper attention because of the focus on irregular migrants when return is equally important to regular migration. According to the official:

For irregular migrants, return should be voluntary- migrants should have sound information and experience no coercion. When all remedies have been exhausted, if a forced return must be implemented, it must respect the rights of the migrants and their families.¹⁴

This is a position on return and while the diplomacy of the AU is not hard, it takes a stance on what the standards of return and readmission procedures are, as well as cooperation and dialogue about it, should be like through the MPFA but also the ongoing processes with RECs, member states, and other national level actors including civil society to create continental guidelines and acceptable standards for return and readmission. This will in turn shape how return diplomacy happens at the supranational level but also bilaterally between AU member states and the EU and its member states but also between AU states themselves. An expert highlighted this as a long-term goal of the AU:

Poorer countries such as Niger can also pick the same document as Nigeria to say that we are negotiating on these terms, and these are the guidelines for return and readmission. If you want to sign an agreement, I am looking carefully to ensure that the agreement has these basic components. I think that's where the documents could be useful. Yeah, they could give a starting point, to give the parameters for certain agreements to be drafted with partners going forward. Some of them are more sophisticated than others but at least this gives a level playing field so that you can pick a document and be guided by it. We are not anticipating that all the arrangements will be the same, there will still be variations but at least the common strands should run through all the agreements and make sure that the minimum standards are met in in the way they relate to countries and then parties outside of the continent, as well as amongst themselves. Yeah, because there's also a lot of abuse. The South African situation is a clear example where you have xenophobic attacks and the rest of it and deportation do not necessarily focus on the human rights of the

¹⁴ Zoom Interview with AUC official, May 15, 2024 (on file with author).

returnees. They should also be held to the same level of accountability as when dealing with external member states or countries. That's what we are hoping will happen.¹⁵

As a result, the envisioned impact of having continental standards is the crystallization of a pan-African approach to return diplomacy that *harmonizes supranational-level ideals with bilateral actions* between member states and towards external actors in Europe, the Middle East, and the rest of the world. The creation of continental standards enables the protection of poor member states from being taken advantage of by powerful external actors who have used funds and other incentives to push their interests in bilateral return negotiations. It also creates a framework through which member states can be *held accountable* for their approaches to return. Nevertheless, the domestic politics of AU member states, as well as mobility agendas that contest the AU's pan-African agenda is a limitation. On the impact of politics, personal mobility agendas, and external influence on member states, an expert stated that:

...They have not been very successful at that because when you are at these meetings, You can see those member states that have been influenced directly by external partners taking a very different stance from the ones who are more into the collective approach to migration governance. These standards are supposed to be for the continent, but some have vested interests and will kick against anything being mandatory, anything that is supposed to be strict in terms of pushing back. They will take exception to that and say it should be up to the member states to decide what to do. Now, if you talk about standards but then also insist that member states should be free to do whatever they want, then what is the impact of those standards? You're talking about harmonizing an approach, but because there is money to be made and because member states have cut separate deals with the EU, they are reluctant to go with a continental approach¹⁶

On the one hand, external actors are undermining both intra and intercontinental return diplomacy and continental standards that protect the rights and dignity of African migrants and impact collective action and cohesion among AU member states. On the other hand, funding and bilateral deals are the weak points of African actors such as Egypt and Tunisia who have recently made deals with the EU to receive loans to support their economies in exchange for implementing the EU's migration management goals.

3.2 Capacity and jurisdiction as limitations to AU return diplomacy

Several actors engaged in the return dialogue raised questions about the AU's jurisdiction on return and readmission. Interviews with an EU official and migration policy experts showed a common view that the AU cannot engage with the EU on return issues because of a lack of jurisdiction and capacity to do so. One of the interviewees stated:

Return is not something we work extensively with the AU because it deals with the readmission of citizens and as a result, requires national competence. The AU is not integrated enough for that competence to pass to the AU. There is no specific AU perspective on return. Still, there is a shared recognition by African countries that return is an important issue- they don't object to their responsibilities and agree on broad principles on returns. The discussion between the EU and AU mostly delineates interests

¹⁵ Zoom Interview with Return and Readmission Expert/ Consultant, July 17, 2024 (on file with author).

¹⁶ Zoom Interview with Return and Readmission Expert/ Consultant, July 17, 2024 (on file with author).

such as legal pathways, not return. I do not foresee a change in AU engagement because it is not a big player in return unless integration elements extend competence to take up these issues. At present, the C2CMMD which is not the most active of dialogues is the main platform between the two; there is a struggle to have regular meetings, and it is left for the AU to steer it. The status quo will not change...¹⁷

A migration policy consultant also agreed that the position of the AU in return diplomacy cannot be more important than that of individual states that must deal with the direct consequences of powerful external actors' interests in return and readmission.¹⁸ This is the reason the AU engages through general principles and norms in the continent whereas hard diplomacy is focused on states. These perspectives reflect an understanding that return, and readmission are a matter of state sovereignty and thus remain beyond the total control of supranational institutions such as the AU- the MPFA itself delineates the link between state sovereignty and return and readmission, which shows that the AU recognizes this limitation, but this is the reason the MPFA focuses on the importance of cooperation, mutual understanding, and enhanced dialogue. An AU diplomacy expert held that it is easier for the AU to work with states and organizations in Africa and beyond negotiating positive solutions such as refugee education but because the return is a morally ambiguous issue, it is harder for the AU to take a hard position on it and as a result, a focus on influencing the behavior and standards around contentious issues such as return becomes the tactic of diplomacy.¹⁹ There are different forms of diplomacy and influencing state behavior and decisions through the creation of standards of operation, norms are on the opposite side of the spectrum of persuasion, which Betts 2011 argues is the inducement and coercion used by powerful actors such as the EU and its member states to shape other states migration policies (p. 38).

The EU also faces challenges due to the bilateral engagements of its member states with third countries to push national return and readmission interests, as a result, even though Europe is more integrated, EU member states still employ diplomacy outside the EU's involvement. This is the challenge of all supranational institutions that must maintain a balance of cohesion and cooperation with the individual interests of member states. The EU and EU member states indeed push for bilateral agreements with individual African states, and these agreements hinder continental goals such as freedom of movement and cohesion in intra-continental approaches, perspectives, and practices. It is also true that the AU is engaging the EU based on the realities delineated by the interviewees. The AU has focused on influencing future return dialogue and cooperation through the MPFA and its revision, the resulting dialogue between the AU and member states, RECs, and other African actors, and the ongoing processes to better delineate an AU-centered approach and standards for return and readmission. This is an indirect way of engaging with the EU and EU member states on return and readmissions- through continental standards, norms, plans of action, guidelines, and consultations with African actors including its members, RECs, civil society, and other domestic-level actors. One of the interviewees concurred with this understanding of the AU's return diplomacy and said:

The AU makes a moral basis, sets principles and standards between African states, and builds positives- which is a good thing and an important role in itself. ²⁰

Influencing and shaping cohesion among all these actors is significant for several reasons, one being the centering of African approaches and perspectives informed by data on RRR programs

¹⁷ Zoom Interview with EU official, March 27, 2024 (on file with author).

¹⁸ Zoom Interview with migration policy consultant, March 28, 2024 (on file with author).

¹⁹ Zoom interview with AU diplomacy expert, July 17, 2024 (on file with author).

²⁰ *ibid.*

and experiences across the continent and clear action points that can be pushed in future dialogue with external actors both at a bilateral, regional and continent-to-continent level.

3.3 The AU and the Constraints of Funding

Pharatlhathe and Vanheukelom (2019) study how funding impacts the governance of the AU, finding that external donors still contribute a substantial part of the AU's funding, and this has consequences not only on the way the institution is governed, what the AU prioritizes and implements but also its relationship with other institutions.²¹ They 'follow the money' and analyze the high dependence of the AU on external funding particularly on the EU- which is the biggest donor to the AU. According to their findings, AU stakeholders felt that external donors such as the EU have been intrusive due to the funding they provide. There are concerns about whether the AU's budget reflects donor preferences, rather than AU priorities.²² While AU has taken steps since 2012 to reduce the dependence on donors, it remains a key challenge today.

This is reflected in opinions about the limitations of the AU's return diplomacy. All the interviewees indicated that funding is the biggest challenge to the AU-EU return diplomacy. An expert on AU relations discussed how both the AU and RECs suffer from a lack of funding, leading them to rely on international donors such as the EU, which hinders the supranational and regional position in return dialogue:

They suffer from a lack of resources, which results in implementation challenges because their members do not have sufficient funding and consequently, they are heavily reliant on international donors. For example, IGAD does not promote return and readmission, it cannot take a hard stance on this issue because it relies on external funds, which is the same for the AU- and an abstention from a position on return is evidence of this limitation.²³

Another interviewee criticized the AU and its member states for wanting to take a stronger stance on return and readmission but relying on donor funding at the same time:

Substantial amounts of the AU funding for their operations come from these same donor agencies anyway so they have a very difficult balancing act to pull off. On the one hand, they want to have an assertive position that these are our standards, and we will not be pushed around but then your operations are being funded by these same people, so they are being diplomatic and saying that, okay, we'll go along with the standards. Because, you know, the EU pushes for national migration policies, labor migration policies, diaspora engagement policies in the name of- If we have clear guidelines and whatnot, maybe they might just limit irregular migration in the process, so they will get IOM to support you, and build capacity so you can develop a national migration policy and most of those policies are looking at international migration, not necessarily internal migration. The AU cannot have a clear position when the EU is giving money for returns... if the AU is not

²¹ The AU's funding comes from two sources: member state contributions and external donor funding. As of 2017, member state contributions constituted 27 percent of the AU's funding, meaning that the remaining comes from donors.

²² PSC Report (2033). Financial independence is key to stronger AU partnerships. Institute for Security Studies ISS Today. Available at: < <https://issafrica.org/iss-today/financial-independence-is-key-to-stronger-au-partnerships>

²³ Zoom interview with AU diplomacy expert, July 17, 2024 (on file with author).

investing in return diplomacy, it is because they understand their strengths and weaknesses.²⁴

According to this critique, both the AU and RECs have focused on international migration, rather than internal migration because of how external funding pushes external agendas on migration in the continent. The interviewee described how for example, Ghanaian actors had to give pushback to European actors to shift the focus on the Ghana National Migration policy from international migration to intra-African migration because while controlling migration to Europe is at the top of the European agenda, internal migration is more important to Ghana. This pushback created a more well-balanced migration policy that spoke to the interests of Ghanaians.

As a result, the future of the AU, its member states, and the RECs approaches to return will depend largely on whether they remain heavily dependent on donor funding. Research supports this conclusion on the impact of funding on supranational diplomacy. States are likely to accommodate the demands and agenda of supranational institutions when they are reliant on the resources of that institution (Lundgren and Wasserfallen 2023).²⁵ The more the AU can fund its agenda, the more it will be able to protect and project its interests and push back against unfavorable agendas. In the relationship between the two supranational institutions, as long as one institution is positioned through funding to create asymmetries of power and push one-sided agendas, the imbalance in diplomacy will continue.

3.4 The role of third parties in AU-EU return diplomacy

The interviews also indicated that third parties (such as EU member states or international organizations) also play a key role in the return dialogue between the AU and EU that should not be ignored. As discussed in earlier sections, actors such as the IOM, the ICMPD, and the Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) have played a role in facilitating the dialogue between the two supranational institutions as well as initiatives such as the C2CMMD. However, some interviewees pointed out a key aspect of this role in the ongoing development of continental standards. An expert on return discusses the indirect role of these actors during the drafting and revision processes:

we had the IOM, the ICMPD, and GIZ being part of the conversation and, you know, these are more or less like proxies for the EU. They tend to be like intermediaries that represent EU interests. So, the EU has been involved from the outset in thinking through these issues. But it has been led mostly by AU member states and then people from the continent. But I imagine the EU interest has always been in the background all along.

As a result, although it looks like the EU is not engaging with the AU in return diplomacy directly, it is pushing its positions through these third parties that act as proxies. Another interviewee gave an example of how the GIZ laid the groundwork for the EU in Ghana:

It's happened in Ghana where we had this engagement with GIZ and they had a physical presence in our Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations. They set up at a center, it was called the Ghana-German Center for Jobs, Migration, and Reintegration, right? And

²⁴ Zoom interview with with Return and Readmission Expert/ Consultant, July 17, 2024 (on file with author).

²⁵ Lundgren, M. and Tallberg, J., & Wasserfallen, F. (2023) Differentiated Influence by Supranational Institutions: Evidence from the European Union. *European Journal of Political Research*, Forthcoming, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4561714>

that seemed to be successful, they managed to get a foothold and there was a very good working relationship between the officials and the ministry. Before long, it was changed to the Ghana- EU Center for Jobs. Yes, so the EU has taken it over, you can see Germany kind of gets in there to soften the ground, and then comes the Big Bang. So, everyone is now on board. It was a Ghana- Germany relationship and then all of a sudden, it became Ghana-EU and that's one of the things that I have been pushing against where they kind of overwhelm one member state.

This is important to note because while there is a distinction between the bilateral negotiations between EU member states and AU member states, bilateral dialogue also fulfills or pushes supranational agendas. Even though there is an ongoing intercontinental dialogue between the AU and EU, picking an AU member state to come to an agreement with is in contradiction to the AU's continental position- this is evident in the Niger and Rwanda examples, among several others. One of the interviewees indicated that one of the blind spots in return diplomacy created by third parties is the targeting of vulnerable, cash-strapped countries in Africa such as Niger, or opportunistic countries in the Global South such as Rwanda to cut deals with and push the European migration control agenda through such countries.²⁶ As a result, bilateral return diplomacy of the EU and its member states challenges the development and implementation of the AU's continental position. The role of third parties in the AU-EU return diplomacy is a two-edged sword, while it has played a significant role in facilitating dialogue between the two supranational institutions on return, "softening the ground" for the migration governance agenda in Europe contributes to an imbalance in the intercontinental and regional return diplomacy.

4. Conclusion: The Partnership Paradox and the Future of AU Return Diplomacy

On the one hand, the AU relies on funding from former colonizers and the EU, which has a return agenda that contrasts with the pan-African agenda of Africans' mobility and freedom of movement. On the other hand, the AU has been pushing back against powerful donors when they overstep boundaries or demand too much (Pharatlhatlhe and Vanheukelom 2019). This tension between agency and reliance is what Pharatlhatlhe and Vanheukelom call the paradox of partnership. According to this perspective, there is never a truly equal partnership, there will always be asymmetries of power at the tip of the scale; donors want some control and participation in the institutions they fund, whereas those receiving funding want autonomy in their engagements. The migration agenda, driven by foreign donors, has led to restrictive migration management in Africa and this is why the role of funding is an important aspect of return diplomacy that future research must delve into.

In return diplomacy with the EU, while negotiations and meetings are crucial, the AU must remain the priority setter because of its pan-African agenda and role as the principle setter/ norm influencer of the continent. This role is crucial in keeping the boundaries between pushback and engagement with foreign partners to protect African sovereignty and migrant rights. The gains from the negotiations and collaboration between the AU and EU do not offset the impact of power asymmetries between the actors in Europe and Africa, but continental standards have the potential to play that role.

²⁶ Zoom interview with with Return and Readmission Expert/ Consultant, July 17, 2024 (on file with author).

The ongoing creation of continental standards, frameworks, protocols, and policies are crucial developments for inter and intra-continental return diplomacy- they can play an essential role as tools that AU member states can use for pushback when they are overwhelmed by the interventions and agendas of powerful actors. Continental standards are the most important aspect of the AU approach to return diplomacy, as a result, if we want to understand the future of AU return diplomacy, we have to follow the development of these standards and what they lead to in the future.

The draft continental guidelines were revised in 2023, and experts hired by the AU have also created support tools to help with operationalizing the guidelines. These support tools include a sample return agreement, a sample standard operating procedure for sustainable reintegration, and terms of reference for national coordinating mechanisms. The guidelines and support tools will go to the AU's Specialized Technical Committees (STC) for review in September this year and then to the AU General Assembly to adopt it as a continental set of guidelines. While the AU tries to play its part in dialogue with the EU and creating standards for member states to refer to, the implementation of these standards and their non-binding nature are where the challenges of the future lie. The work of the AU and its pan-African approach to return diplomacy with the EU is cut out in the operationalization of the continental guidelines and getting Member States to adhere to a continental agenda in their bilateral engagements with external actors at different levels. If the operationalization of the continental guidelines is successful, a more consolidated return diplomacy approach in Africa is possible.

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